

Introduction to Engineering Design

Chapter 4

Engineering Design Process & Components

Lecturer: Mirzi Betasolo, Ph.D (TM), MEng, GE, CE

Learning Objectives to be achieved:

1. To identify and apply the various phases and processes within an engineering design process
2. To have practical application or practice engineering design process
3. To identify engineering design components
4. Applying engineering design processes and components in addressing action on any Sustainable Development Goals.

4.0 Introduction

This fourth week's topics respond to the first-course objective, "To identify and apply the various phases and processes within an engineering design process".

- *Most engineering designs can be classified as inventions-devices or systems that are created by human effort and did not exist before or are improvements over existing devices or systems.*
- *We described engineers primarily as problem solvers.*

4.1 Engineering Design Process

5 Phases of Engineering Design Process-

Figure 18. 5 Phases of Engineering Design Process
<http://www.eie.org/overview/engineering-design-process>

4.1.1 ASK

- **What is the problem?**

Approach to the problem: (Benavides, 2012)

- ✓ **Motivation.** Cause, reason, or purpose that moves something.
- ✓ **Need or list of needs.** Those circumstances, conditions, characteristics, qualities, or demands may not be lacking without distorting the description of the motivation.
- ✓ **List of requirements.** In the context of Axiomatic Design, circumstances or conditions are necessary for describing the motivation. It differs from the list of needs because it has additional limitations: they must comprise a minimum, independent list.
- ✓ **Constraints.** Those needs are not included in the list of requirements. Terms relating to the approach to the response:
- ✓ **Satisfy.** To provide a solution to a motivation problem by meeting the needs, requirements and constraints.
- ✓ **Solve.** To provide a solution to a difficulty arising from a motivation, considering the needs, requirements and constraints. The difference concerning 'satisfy' is that although the needs, conditions and limitations are taken into account, compliance is not assured.

- How have others approached it?

To know how others had approached the problem, research must be conducted by reviewing literature related to the topic of interest.

Literature Review

Definition: A literature review is **a survey of scholarly sources (such as books, journal articles, and theses) related to a specific topic or research question.** It is often written as part of a thesis, dissertation, or research paper, to situate your work about existing knowledge (How to Write a Literature Review | Guide, Examples, & Templates)

A literature review has four main objectives: (What is a literature review?)

- ✓ It **surveys** the literature in your chosen area of study (demonstrates a familiarity with a body of knowledge and establishes the credibility of your work)
- ✓ It **synthesises** the information in that literature into a summary (summarises prior research and says how your project is linked to it)
- ✓ It **critically analyses** the information gathered by identifying gaps in current knowledge by showing limitations of theories and points of view; and by formulating areas for further research and reviewing areas of controversy (integrates and summarises what is known about a subject)
- ✓ It **presents** the literature in an organised way (demonstrates that you have learnt from others and that your research is a starting point for new ideas)

There are five key steps to writing a literature review: (How to Write a Literature Review | Guide, Examples, & Templates)

1. **Search** for relevant literature (engine search, Mendeley, Google scholar, ResearchGate, etc)
2. **Evaluate** sources (to keep track of your references with citations to avoid plagiarism)
For each publication, ask yourself:
 - ✓ What question or problem is the author addressing?
 - ✓ What are the key concepts, and how are they defined?
 - ✓ What are the key theories, models, and methods?
 - ✓ Does the research use established frameworks or take an innovative approach?
 - ✓ What are the results and conclusions of the study?
 - ✓ How does the publication relate to other literature in the field? Does it confirm, add to, or challenge established knowledge?
 - ✓ What are the strengths and weaknesses of the research?

3. **Identify** themes, debates, and gaps.

Based on your reading and notes, you can look for the following:

- ✓ Trends and patterns (in theory, method or results): do certain approaches become more or less popular over time?
- ✓ Themes: what questions or concepts recur across the literature?
- ✓ Debates, conflicts and contradictions: where do sources disagree?
- ✓ Pivotal publications: are there any influential theories or studies that changed the direction of the field?
- ✓ Gaps: what is missing from the literature? Are there weaknesses that need to be addressed?

Examples of trends and gaps,

In reviewing the literature on social media and body image, you note that:

- ✓ Most research has focused on young women.
- ✓ There is an increasing interest in the visual aspects of social media.
- ✓ But there is still a lack of robust research on highly visual platforms like Instagram and Snapchat—this gap you could address in your research.

4. **Outline** the structure

-**Chronological** (analyse patterns, turning points and key debates that have shaped the direction of the field. Give your interpretation of how and why certain developments occurred)

-**Thematic** (organise your literature review into subsections that address different aspects of the topic)

-**Methodological** (will bring you to create a conceptual framework for your study)

Suppose you draw your sources from disciplines or fields using various research methods. In that case, you might want to compare the results and conclusions from different approaches. For example:

- Look at what results have emerged in qualitative versus quantitative research
- Discuss how the topic has been approached by empirical versus theoretical scholarship
- Divide the literature into sociological, historical, and cultural sources

-**Theoretical** (will bring you to create a theoretical framework for your research)

A literature review is often the foundation for a theoretical framework. You can use it to discuss various theories, models, and definitions of key concepts.

5. **Write** your literature review.

In doing so, note the following:

Summarise and synthesise: give an overview of the main points of each source and combine them into a coherent whole

Analyse and interpret: don't just paraphrase other researchers—add your interpretations where possible, discussing the significance of findings concerning the literature as a whole

Critically evaluate: mention the strengths and weaknesses of your sources

Write in well-structured paragraphs: use transition words and topic sentences to draw connections, comparisons and contrasts

- **What are the constraints?**

Definition: A *constraint* **limits or controls what you can do**. Example, the decision to abandon the trip was cause of financial constraints. (constraint)

4.1.2 IMAGINE

- **What are the solutions?**
 - ✓ Develop as many solutions as possible. (Engineering Design Process)

- **Brainstorm ideas**
 - ✓ Encourage wild ideas and defer judgment! (Engineering Design Process)
 - ✓ Build on the ideas of others (stay focused on a topic) (Engineering Design Process)
- **Choose the best one**
 - ✓ For many teams, this is the hardest step! Revisit the needs, constraints and research from the earlier efforts, compare your best ideas, select one solution and make a plan to move forward with it. (Engineering Design Process)

4.1.3 PLAN

- ✓ ***Conceptual or preliminary design:*** The objective is to choose one of all the possible solutions. Most of the main characteristics of a design are determined during this stage, which usually represents a small fraction of the total time occupied by the design process. This stage encompasses up to step 7 (selection). The information output is the optimum solution or frozen configuration. (Benavides, 2012)
- ✓ ***Detailed design:*** With most of the crucial decisions established in the preliminary design, we get what could be called a 'frozen design.' It is the time to create engineering (mathematical) models that enable us to analyse the elements of the system and the system itself. Because these models are complex and expensive, it would be desirable if the frozen design did not require modifications following the detailed analysis to fine-tune the parameters. The information output is the set of drawings, manuals and instructions that enable us to perform the tasks leading to placing an operational product on the market. (Benavides, 2012)

4.1.4 CREATE

- ✓ ***Build a Prototype:*** Building a prototype makes your ideas real! These early versions of the design solution help your team verify whether the design meets the original challenge objectives. Push yourself for creativity, imagination and excellence in design. (Engineering Design Process)
- ✓ ***Test and Evaluate Prototype:*** Does it work? Does it solve the need? Communicate the results and get feedback. Analyse and talk about what works, what doesn't and what could be improved. (Engineering Design Process)

4.1.5 IMPROVE

- ✓ ***Redesign as Needed:*** Discuss how you could improve your solution. Make revisions. Draw new designs. Iterate your design to make your product the best it can be. (Engineering Design Process)

4.2 Engineering Design Components

4.2.1 Need & Impact

✓ **SDG's**

SDG definition:

"Meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs" (1987: Bruntland Report)

Figure 19. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals
The concept of Greening Engineering discussed in weeks one and two should be included in the engineering design process (Betasolo et al. 2017).

✓ Customer's Needs

Customer Needs Definition: A customer need is **a need that motivates a customer to purchase a product or service**. The need can be known (i.e., the customer can put it into words) or unknown and is the ultimate factor determining which solution the customer purchases. (Stobierski)

3 Main Types of Customer Needs (Stobierski)

- ✓ 1. *Functional Needs*. Functional needs are the most tangible and evident of the three main types of customer needs. Customers evaluate potential solutions based on whether they'll help them achieve a particular task or function. The product or service that best addresses their functional need is likely to be the one they purchase or hire. Depending on the customer's buying criteria, functional needs can be broad or extremely specific.
- ✓ 2. *Social Needs*. A social need is a customer need that relates to how a person wants to be perceived by others when using a product or service. While social needs aren't typically a customer's primary concern when considering a purchase, they can influence their final decision. Social needs are often more difficult for a company to identify and vary substantially from customer to customer. Understanding various social needs allows you to look for patterns among your users. If enough of your customers share a particular need, consider how it can inform your product development, sales, and marketing processes.
- ✓ 3. *Emotional Needs*. Emotional needs are similar to social conditions, typically secondary to functional requirements. Whereas social needs refer to how a customer wants to be perceived by others when using a product, emotional needs refer to how a customer wants to feel.

4.2.2 Cost

✓ Economic Analysis

In economic analyses, it is vital to recognise the time value of money. Because of interest, a quantity of money is worth more now than the prospect of receiving the same amount later. Economic studies may be used: (Wright, 2002)

- ✓ To determine the feasibility of a project.
- ✓ To compare alternate designs.
- ✓ To determine the priority of construction of a group of projects.
- ✓ To evaluate specific features of the design.

- In any product development, materials cost is also generally a limiting factor. While cost is universally recognised and perhaps the easiest of all properties to understand, there are specific cost considerations for materials selection. Just as materials and their processing go hand in hand, so do material costs and processing costs. Understanding the entire processing sequence is critical to accurately evaluating a material's cost.

4.2.3 Elements

✓ **Materials:**

- Material means a substance of which something is composed or made. As we begin the 21st century, advances in materials research and technology offer great promise.
- Material strength to sustain load needs to be determined to minimise the risk of the limitation of the material under applied load.
- In service behaviour is the behaviour of the material during the time of service or period of use. In this world, everything has an end. All kinds of materials come to an end or their usability. In-service behaviour is also defined as the insufficient load-bearing capacity or inadequate structure or structural element serviceability. Therefore when a material is incapable of executing its normal functions, it is described as having failed.
- Insufficient load capacity means that the material's components cannot withstand the load acting on the material.
- Failure occurs due to various causes. These may be due to fracture, excessive deformation due to plastic deformation or dimensional changes with time, instability or buckling, loss of material by corrosion, erosion or abrasive serviceability is defined as the ability of structure or structural element to perform adequately for normal intended use under all expected actions during the lifetime of the structure. Serviceability failure occurs when the material or composite of materials of the structure fails.
- Material failure wear or alteration of properties due to environmental effects. The failure modes may depend on stress, time, temperature, environment, or any combination of these factors. Thus, it is vital to understand the mechanics of the various failure modes.
- Modes of Failure
 - Failure by Yielding
 - Failure by fracture
 - Failure by creep
 - Failure by Fatigue
 - Failure by corrosion

- **Failure by Yielding.** Is the failure occurrence reaching above the yield point. Yielding failure occurs when a material subject to mechanical loading exhibits sufficient plastic deformation such that it can no longer perform its intended function. Once yielding has occurred, the material is said to be plastic, and the deformation and strains are referred to as plastic. This failure mode results in deflected, stretched, or otherwise misshapen components and is typical in ductile materials such as metals and polymers.
- **Failure by Fracture.** Fracture is the act of concentration of stress point, which causes total disintegration. Some of the commercial materials contain internal cracks and other defects. Stress concentration occurs at any sharp corner or edges of holes. At such points, the stress may be several times larger than the stress which would otherwise be expected. A ductile fracture occurs when a material experiences substantial plastic deformation or strain while being stressed beyond its yield strength and is consequently torn into pieces. When this material is subjected to stress, cracks propagate either by ductile tearing or cleavage.

The ductile tearing type occurs in ductile materials, and considerable energy is absorbed in deforming plastic material just ahead of a growing crack. The plastic deformation tends to round off the crack's tip, consequently reducing the stress concentration effect. However, severe plastic deformation tends to create cavities adjacent to the crack's tip and eventually leads to fracture. In contrast, in brittle material, no or little plastic deformation occurs at the crack's tip. If the local stress exceeds the cleavage fracture stress of the metal, inter-atomic bonds are broken, the crack develops catastrophically, and sudden brittle failure occurs.

Griffith's equation follows a relationship for plate-like components for brittle materials to find the critical size of the crack for a fast fracture to occur.

$$\sigma_c = [(2 \gamma E)/(\pi a)]^{1/2}$$

where:

σ_c – is the critical stress for fracture

γ – is the fracture surface energy per unit area

E – is the modulus of elasticity of the material and

a – is one-half of the crack length

For metals that undergo plastic flow, the crack develops at the tip; thus the equation is"

$$\sigma_c = [(2 (\gamma + \gamma_p) E) / (\pi a)]^{1/2}$$

where:

γ_p – is the work done in plastic deformation per unit area of crack extension

- **Failure by creep.** Factors affecting the amount of creep are time, stress and temperature. Relaxation is a phenomenon associated with and related to creep. Examples of relaxation are a reduction in stress levels in tensioned bolts over extended periods in service and stress reduction in pre-stressed bars and cables in pre-stressed concrete construction.
- **Failure by fatigue.** Is the repetitive failure during loadings such as bridges and rotating machineries like pumps and turbines are subjected to repetitive or cyclic stresses. This type of failure results from crack formation in a region of high stress and subsequent growth due to repetitive loading, resulting in the crack growth and loss of stiffness of the structure failing. The existence of crack may be due to the crack nucleation and growth or due to manufacturing defects. The final failure is sudden, and the fracture is usually of cleavage type.

Other factors that affect fatigue strength are the metal's surface condition and the environment's nature. The presence of scratches or notches acts as points of stress raisers for the initiation of cracks, and the fatigue strength is reduced greatly. However, ductile materials are much less sensitive to surface flaws than brittle materials.

- **Failure by Corrosion.** In a structure subjected to cyclic stressing in conditions in which corrosion can occur, the corrosion rate is increased, and failure occurs due to material loss. Or it is a loss of material due to alteration of mechanical properties.
- **Failures Recorded example:**
 - May 16, 1988 (Reuters, Mining Accidents) news that ten black gold miners were hurled into an underground elevator on Saturday and fell to their death at the bottom of a mile deep shaft when a descending hit the obstruction at the Harmony gold mine was cause of the accident according to Martin Faillon, a spokesperson for the Rand Mines group.
 - August 7, 2008 (Associated Press, Mining Accidents) reported that the collapse of the Crandall Canyon one year ago was so extensive

that federal officials found no other mining disaster in the last 50 yrs to compare to it. Hundreds of coal pillars, overloaded by aggressive mining that curved out too many voids, collapsed within seconds on August 6, 2007, entombing six miners nearly half a half-mile underground. Satellite images show that a 69-acre section of the mine caved in, about the equivalent of 63 football fields.

- December 10, __ (Times Wire Reports, Mining Accidents) reported that eleven Chinese miners were trapped underground for nearly six days by a tunnel collapse, ate paper and chewed on a boiled leather belt to ease their hunger. A 33 yr old miner Wu Pengyong was quoted saying, "At first we ate newspaper pages, then orange peel." The miners were pulled from the illegal iron and gold mine in northern China after six days.
- Failure by ductile:
 - An oil tanker (The New York Times) was reported to split in half by crack propagation around its girth. The fractures occur along grain boundary due to fracture failures, fatigue and creep. Ductile fractures are almost always preferred for two reasons. First, brittle fracture occurs suddenly and catastrophically without warning, resulting in spontaneous and rapid crack propagation. On the other hand, for ductile fracture, the presence of plastic deformation warns that fracture is imminent, allowing preventive measures to be taken. Second, more strain energy is required to induce ductile fracture as much as ductile materials are generally tougher. Under applied tensile stress, most metal alloys are ductile, whereas ceramics are notably brittle, and polymers may exhibit both types of fractures.

✓ **Functionality:**

Definition: Functionality refers to whether a design works and helps the users meet their goals and needs. (What is Functionality?)

The elements of **functional design** is the process of responding to the needs or desires of the people who will use an item in a way that allows their needs or desires to be met. *Functional design* is both an outcome and a process. As an *outcome*, it describes products that work well to perform their assigned tasks; as a *process*, functional design is a set of practices guided by the principles that produce that positive outcome. (Wax)

To create a product that *works*, there are seven questions you should keep in mind about the product you're designing, who will be using it, and how they'll be using it. (Wax)

- Consider The Product's Goal
- Consider Who Will Be Using It?

- Consider What Your Audience Intends To Do With It?
- Is It Clear, How To Use It?
- How Does Your User Know It's Working?
- Is It Engaging To Your Users?
- How Does It Handle Mistakes?

✓ Design Thinking:

Definition: Design thinking is a **non-linear, iterative process that teams use to understand users, challenge assumptions, redefine problems and create innovative solutions to prototype and test.** (What is Design Thinking?)

Design thinking's value as a world-improving, driving force in business (global heavyweights such as Google, Apple and Airbnb have wielded it to notable effect) matches its status as a popular subject at leading international universities. **With design thinking, teams have the freedom to generate ground-breaking solutions.** Using it, your team can get behind hard-to-access insights and apply a collection of hands-on methods to help find innovative answers. (What is Design Thinking?)

References

(n.d.). Retrieved from Type of Engineering Design: <https://www.mcgill.ca/engineeringdesign/step-step-design-process/design-definitions-and-terminology/types-engineering-design>

(n.d.). Retrieved from Sustainable Development Goals Booklet: <https://www.undp.org/publications/sustainable-development-goals-booklet>

(n.d.). Retrieved from PNG Exploration and Development Activities Accelerates: <http://www.womp-int.com/story/2009vol10/story002.htm>

1987: *Brundtland Report*. (n.d.). Retrieved from Sustainable Development: <https://www.are.admin.ch/are/en/home/media/publications/sustainable-development/brundtland-report.html>

Benavides, E. (2012). *Advance Engineering Design*. Woodhead Publishing Limited.

Betasolo, M., & Chris Kobal, W. P. (n.d.). "Greening Civil": An applied Climate Change Mitigation Program at PNGUoT. *1st SERI Conference 2018*.

Climate Change. (n.d.). Retrieved from http://www.occd.gov.pg/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=39&Itemid=66

constraint. (n.d.). Retrieved from Collins:

<https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/constraint#:~:text=A%20constraint%20is%20something%20that,rein%20More%20Synonyms%20of%20constraint>

designtechsystem.com. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.designtechsys.com/articles/engineering-design-services#:~:text=The%20importance%20of%20Engineering%20Design,-While%20the%20spoon&text=The%20fundamental%20elements%20of%20the,the%20solution%20of%20technical%20problems>.

Engineering Design Process. (n.d.). Retrieved from Teach Engineering:

<https://www.teachengineering.org/populartopics/designprocess#>

How to Write a Literature Review | Guide, Examples, & Templates. (n.d.). Retrieved from Scribbr:

[https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/literature-review/#:~:text=A%20literature%20review%20is%20a%20survey%20of%20scholarly%20sources%20\(such,in%20relation%20to%20existing%20knowledge](https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/literature-review/#:~:text=A%20literature%20review%20is%20a%20survey%20of%20scholarly%20sources%20(such,in%20relation%20to%20existing%20knowledge)

Stobierski, T. (n.d.). *3 MOST COMMON TYPES OF CUSTOMER NEEDS TO BE AWARE OF*. Retrieved from

Harvard Business School Online: <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/types-of-customer-needs#:~:text=What%20Are%20Customer%20Needs%3F,which%20solution%20the%20custome r%20purchases>.

Wax, D. M. (n.d.). *7 Essential Guideline for Functional Design*. Retrieved from

<https://www.smashingmagazine.com/2008/08/7-essential-guidelines-for-functional-design/>

What is a literature review? (n.d.). Retrieved from Royal Literary Fund:

<https://www.rlf.org.uk/resources/what-is-a-literature-review/>

What is Design Thinking? (n.d.). Retrieved from Interactive Design Foundation: <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/design-thinking#:~:text=Design%20thinking%20is%20a%20non,are%20ill%2Ddefined%20or%20unknown>

What is Functionality? (n.d.). Retrieved from Interaction Design Foundation: <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/functionality>

Wright, P. H. (2002). *Introduction to Engineering Design*. John Wiley & Sons.